

Supplementary Information

Monitoring Transient Changes in the Structure of Water at a Polarised Liquid-Liquid Interface using Electrocapillary Curves

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S1 Supplementary experimental methods

S1.1 Materials

All chemicals were used as received without further purification. All aqueous solutions were prepared with ultra-pure water (Millipore Milli-Q, specific resistivity 18.2 M Ω ·cm). Bis(triphenylphosphoranylidene) ammonium chloride (BACl, 97%) and lithium tetrakis(pentafluorophenyl)borate diethyletherate ([Li(OEt₂)]TB) were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich and Boulder Scientific Company, respectively. Bis(triphenylphosphoranylidene)ammonium tetrakis(pentafluorophenyl)borate (BATB) was prepared by metathesis of equimolar solutions of BACl and [Li(OEt₂)]TB in a methanol-water (2:1 v/v) mixture. The resulting precipitates were filtered, washed, recrystallised from acetone and finally washed 5 times with methanol-water (2:1 v/v) mixture. Lithium chloride (LiCl, $\geq 95\%$), tetraethylammonium chloride (TEACl, $\geq 98\%$), lithium sulfate (Li₂SO₄, $\geq 98.5\%$), methane sulfonic acid (MSA, $\geq 99\%$), and sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄, 95-98%) were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich. The organic solvent α,α,α -trifluorotoluene (TFT, 99+%) was obtained from Acros Organics.

S1.2 Electrochemical measurements

Electrochemical experiments were carried out at the water| α,α,α -trifluorotoluene interface using a four-electrode configuration (the geometric area of the cell was 1.60 cm²). To supply the current flow, platinum counter electrodes were positioned in the organic and aqueous phases. The potential drop at the L-L interface was measured by means of *pseudo*-reference silver/silver chloride (Ag/AgCl) electrodes, which were connected to the aqueous and organic phases, respectively, through Luggin capillaries. In some experiments Ag/AgX reference electrodes were used, where X is the anion with the highest concentration in the aqueous phase, to ensure reference potential stability. The Galvani potential difference was attained by assuming the formal ion transfer potential of TEA⁺ to be 0.149 V [1]. The general configuration of the cell is outlined in Scheme 1, see Section 2.1 main text.

Differential capacitances at different applied voltages were measured using alternating current (AC) voltammetry, also known as potentiodynamic electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), also known as AC voltammetry, at 10 Hz and assuming the

cell behaves as a series R-C circuit. At this frequency, the contribution of faradic processes is significant only at the edge of the potential window.

S1.3 Molecular modelling

In this study, we used atomistic molecular dynamics (MD) computer simulations to model the dynamics of methanesulfonate ions (MS^-) at the liquid-liquid interface between water and TFT. CGenFF [2] potentials were used for MS^- and the TIP3P model [3] was used for water. TFT, BA^+ and TB^- models were generated from existing CGenFF data and further refined with QM calculations (MP2/CC-PVTZ), carried out using Gaussian [4]. Charges were obtained by fitting using the approaches of Merz-Singh-Kollman [5,6], CHELPG [7], and natural orbital analysis. To reproduce experimental conditions as closely as possible, the bottom half of a 10 x 10 x 20 nm box was filled with TFT and the top half with water. To ensure there is only a single interface, periodic boundary conditions (PBC) were used in the x and y directions but not in the z direction normal to the plane of the interface. Instead, two walls were used, one at the bottom and one at the top. The walls interact with the system *via* a mild repulsive Lennard-Jones potential. Two systems were considered, a system with only the two neat solvents forming the interface, which is used as reference (system A), and another which contained solutes, BA^+ and TB^- in TFT, and MS^- and Na^+ in water (system B). For the latter, 542 MS^- ions were randomly inserted in the water side of the box and neutralised with 542 Na^+ counter-ions. This corresponds to a concentration 100 times higher than the solution used in the experiments. This higher concentration is used to take into account the gradient of concentration of MSA in water when interfaced with TFT, diffusion and transfer phenomena increased by the external potential applied on the cell during the experiments, and finally to speed up the sampling of the system and obtain a computationally tractable spontaneous migration of the MS^- ions at the interface. The Particle Mesh Ewald method [8] is used to treat long-range electrostatics. High frequency bonds to hydrogen were constrained using the LINCS [9] algorithm which allowed the use of a two femtosecond (2 fs) time step to integrate the equations of motion. The simulation cells were equilibrated and thermalised over one nanosecond of molecular dynamics to obtain a stable constant pressure-temperature (NPT) [10,11] ensemble at 1 atm and 300K. All simulations were carried out using Gromacs MD code version 2018-3 [12,13].

S2 Correlating interfacial energy and differential capacitance

In order to closely correlate the interfacial energy and capacitance, the only work done on the system is typically assumed to be that required to change the interfacial area or interfacial energy [14]. However, this assumption does not hold true as during a potential scan, additional changes also take place. The internal energy changes with the applied potential because of the external polarisation (this statement is related to the energy conservation law). A factor which effects the mutual solubility between any two immiscible solvents is the presence of a third component, such as a surfactant [15]. For experiments at the ITIES, another type of third component is the presence of electrolyte ions in each phase. Upon external polarisation of the ITIES, the distribution and flux of the ions between the two phases changes with the applied potential. For example, at positive potentials from the PZC, Li^+ ions cross the interface. However, Li^+ does not cross alone during ion transfer, it brings water in its solvation shell to the organic phase [16]. Thus, due to this movement of ions, it is extremely unlikely that the concentration of water in the oil phase close to the interface remains constant upon polarisation. Thus, as the composition of the solvents and ions changes upon polarisation, the local internal energy at the interface has to change because it depends on composition. In other words, the internal energy of both solvents changes because the polarity of each solvent close to the interface is not constant and the mutual solubility between solvents changes upon applied potential. As discussed in more detail *vide infra*, the nanoscopic effect of these changes is that the hydrogen bonding of water close to the interface changes depending on the distribution of ions inside the electrical double layer.

On the other hand, the classical deduction of capacitance from an electrocapillary curve assumes interfacial energy decreases as the surface electric charge increases, but this is not always the case. Ghosal *et al.* [17] reported an enhancement of anion concentration, with a concomitant increase of interfacial energy, at the water vapour interface of solutions of potassium halides. Such an enhancement appears contrary to expectations from classical thermodynamic [18], but arises because the complexity associated with water structure and solvent-ion interactions are not taken into account in the classical theoretical description of electrocapillary curves [17]. Furthermore, the classical deduction of the electrocapillary equation does not take into account the contribution of the change of the chemical potential

of the solvent at the interface on the surface tension, it only takes only into account the chemical potential of electrons and ions [19].

It has been proposed that the capacitances measured by AC voltammetry are affected by mechano–electric oscillations [21]. This model states that the periodic change of the applied AC voltage changes the surface energy periodically, thereby inducing a periodic change of the mean amplitude of the capillary waves, *i.e.*, the apparent width of the interface. The model assumes that this width represents the mean charge separation between the two electrolyte solutions, *i.e.*, the thickness of the ion-free inner layer, which is linked to the surface dipole potential. It means that the interfacial capacitance depends on both the Gouy-Chapman capacitance and on the capacitance associated with the ionic polarisation induced by the change of amplitude of the capillary waves generated by the AC voltage. This model suggests that the capacitances measured by AC voltammetry are going to be higher than those measured by electrocapillary experiments, where the AC oscillation is absent. However, this interpretation assumes that the surface energy changes in phase with the applied voltage at all frequencies, which is unlikely. All polarisation phenomena have a characteristic frequency where the resonance between the polarisation and the external electric field is the highest [22,23].

S3 Supplementary figures

Fig.S1. Differential capacitance curve when the aqueous electrolyte in Scheme 1 is 10.6 mM LiCl. The dashed red line represents the potential of zero charge (PZC) on the Galvani scale (0.149 V).

Fig. S2. (a) Computed order parameter of water (red) and of MS^- (green) in system B. (b) Computed angle between the dipole moment of water and the z -axis (red), and between the C-S axis of MSA and the z -axis (green), in system B.

The orientation of the molecules in the layers is monitored by three properties: the average dipole moment along the ITIES, the average angle θ formed by the molecule main axis with the plane normal to the ITIES, here the z -axis, and the corresponding order parameter $s = (3 \cos^2 \theta - 1)/2$. The order parameter varies between -0.5, which indicates that the vector of reference is orthogonal to the normal, and 1, which indicates that the vector of reference is collinear to the normal. For water, the dipole moment is usually used as the vector of reference. For MS^- ,

the vector formed by the C and S atoms is used in the present study. Fig. S2a depicts the order parameter for water (red) and MS^- (green) in system B. At the interface, water order parameter shows a negative peak with a minimum at -0.15 suggesting that the water dipole moment is almost orthogonal to the z-axis. By contrast, the MS^- order parameter shows a large peak with a maximum at 0.45 suggesting that the molecule C-S axis is relatively co-linear to the z-axis. The distribution of tilt angles in Fig. S2b shows a more detailed structure of water with two peaks with maxima at 94 and 96 degrees and a single peak for MS^- at 40 degrees.

Supplementary References

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